

HEATS OF WETTING OF POROUS BODIES BY WATER AND METHYL ALCOHOL

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Heats of wetting by water and methyl alcohol were determined in the case of three samples of charcoal, a sample of bentonite and a sample each of silica, alumina, ferric oxide and chromic oxide gels before as well as after associating them with varying amounts of water and methyl alcohol. The thermal effect in the case of dry adsorbents was more with methyl alcohol than with water, and for a given liquid was found to depend upon the surface area of the adsorbent which, in fact, could be thus estimated. The measurement of heats of wetting of the solid as a function of the amounts of liquids previously adsorbed permitted calculations of heats of adsorption of monolayers of liquid (from the liquid phase) and isosteric heats of adsorption. There is no relationship between the heat of adsorption of a liquid in the monolayer and its heat of fusion, as pointed out by previous workers. Isosteric heats of adsorption are positive and tend to drop to zero after the completion of the monolayer.

In a previous communication (Puri, Gupta and Lakhanpal, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 435) it has been shown that heat of immersion of charcoal in water depends largely on its water isotherm as a whole and not on any single point on the graph. Now, since the adsorption isotherm itself depends on surface area of the solid, as shown by Boyd and Harkins (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 1190) and Kistler, Fischer and Freeman (*ibid.*, 1943, 65, 1909), there should be some relationship between heat of immersion of a dry solid in a wetting liquid and its surface area. Some investigators have noted a sort of dependence of heat of immersion on particle size (Parkes, *Phil. Mag.*, 1902, vi, 4, 240; Iliin *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1937, vii, 23, 294) or even surface area (Iliin, Kiselev, Likhachava and Scherhakova, *Doklady Akad. Nauk. S.S.S.R.*, 1950, 75, 827), but the exact relationship between these quantities does not appear to have been worked out and the possibility of determining surface area of powders by this simple technique has not been explored.

Stowe (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, 56, 487) and Puri *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), from measurements of the heats of immersion as a function of the amount of water pre-adsorbed on the solid, have shown that the heat of formation of a monolayer of water (derived from liquid water), in the case of alumina gels and charcoal, is nearly twice the heat of fusion of ice. This relationship, however, needs verification by carrying out similar investigations on other solid-liquid systems as well.

By combining heats of immersion data with the results obtained from an adsorption isotherm at one temperature, it is possible to calculate isosteric heats of adsorption (Jura and Hill, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 1598). This procedure was utilised by Young *et al.* (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, 58, 313) in calculating isosteric heats of adsorption of water on graphon, which was found to be negative. It will be of interest to make similar calculations in the case of porous adsorbents which have large areas and high adsorption capacities.

The work described in this paper was undertaken with these objectives in view.

EXPERIMENTAL

Three samples of charcoal (prepared by the carbonisation of cane sugar, coconut shell and pine wood), a sample of bentonite, and gels of silica, alumina, ferric oxide and chromic oxide, prepared by the usual precipitation methods and dried to constant weights at 110°, were used in these investigations. Water (redistilled) and methyl alcohol (Merck's extra pure, free from acetone) were used as the wetting liquids. Heats of wetting of the various samples, when dry and when different amounts of water (or methyl alcohol) had been pre-adsorbed on them in equilibrium with atmospheres of different relative vapour pressures at 25° (Puri, Lakhanpal and Verma, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 841), were determined in water as well as in methyl alcohol by using the same technique as described in the previous communication (*loc. cit.*). Surface areas of the various samples were calculated from their water and methyl alcohol isotherms by following Boyd and Harkins' calculations (*loc. cit.*) and a mean value was taken in each case.

DISCUSSION

Heat of Wetting and Surface Area.—The heats of wetting of the oven-dried samples in water and methyl alcohol are shown in Table I. It is seen that in every case more heat is evolved in methyl alcohol than in water. The adsorbability of methyl alcohol was also found to be greater than that of water, particularly in the lower parts of the isotherms. This may explain higher thermal values in methyl alcohol.

The thermal values, expressed in terms of ergs/cm², are also included in Table I.

TABLE I
Heats of wetting of the dry adsorbents by water and methyl alcohol.

Adsorbent.	Surface area (mg./g.).	Heat of wetting (cal./g.) by		Heat of wetting (ergs./cm ²) by	
		Water.	MeOH.	Water.	MeOH.
Alumina gel	236.6	17.93	19.50	318.2	345.3
Silica gel	339.7	25.75	38.25	318.8	440.4
Chromic oxide gel	150.3	11.02	15.67	308.6	438.6
Ferric oxide gel	204.9	14.50	19.83	296.1	396.7
Bentonite	138.8	9.95	11.85	301.4	358.1
Sugar charcoal	180.5	12.30	18.91	290.6	440.1
Pine charcoal	123.4	9.18	13.82	312.7	433.3
Coconut charcoal	139.1	9.59	14.88	289.9	449.9

It is interesting to note that the values in a given liquid, particularly in water, are fairly close to one another, irrespective of the surface area or the nature of the adsorbent. This shows that the heat of immersion is largely a surface phenomenon and that the surfaces involved in the experiments are all alike. An average value of 305 ergs may be taken for wetting 1 sq. cm. of surface in water. This is quite significant since it enables one to calculate surface areas of porous bodies from a single value, namely, heat of wetting in water. In order to verify this a few more samples of charcoal, soils and gels (prepared by different methods) were taken. Their water isotherms as well as heats of immersion in water were determined. The surface areas calculated from the isotherms by Boyd and Harkins' method and from the heats of wetting are compared in Table II. The agreement is seen to be as good as could be expected.

This places at our disposal quite a convenient method for estimating surface areas of porous bodies.

TABLE II

Comparison of surface areas determined from heats of wetting in water and from water isotherms by Harkin's method.

Adsorbent.	Surface area (m ² /g.) calc. from		Adsorbent.	Surface area (m ² /g.) calc. from	
	Heat of wetting.	Water isotherm.		Heat of wetting.	Water isotherm.
Alumina (from potash alum)	259.7	280.6	Ferric oxide (from ferric alum precipitated at 100°)	159.7	140.8
Alumina (from aluminium amalgam)	231.9	242.7	Sugar charcoal (activated)	210.6	241.6
Alumina (from aluminium butoxide)	212.3	218.2	Acacia wood charcoal	124.4	164.7
Chromic oxide (from chrome alum)	142.7	160.7	Cotton stalk charcoal	118.1	142.5
Chromic oxide (from chrome alum precipitated at 100°)	139.9	126.2	α-Stannic acid	101.5	89.98
Ferric oxide (from ferric alum)	198.9	232.1	β-Stannic acid	121.7	109.4
			Soil P.C. 13	149.8	150.8
			Soil P.C. 19	106.9	88.9

Calculation of Heat of Adsorption of a Monolayer (from liquid phase).—The heat effects on immersing silica gel and bentonite with different surface coverage in water and methyl alcohol are shown graphically in Fig. 1. The other adsorbents showed similar results (not included for reasons of space). It is evident (Fig. 1) that the heat of immersion of a solid decreases appreciably when it contains even a small amount of the liquid pre-adsorbed on it.

FIG. 1

Heat of wetting as a function of the amount of the liquid previously adsorbed.

The amounts of water and methyl alcohol required to form monolayers in the case of the various adsorbents were calculated, assuming that a molecule of water covers 10A^2 and that of methyl alcohol 16A^2 (Brunauer, "Adsorption of Gases and Vapours", Vol. I, 1942, Princeton Univ. Press). The heats of wetting of the various samples, when they already contained these amounts of the liquids, were read from the respective graphs, and subtracting these from the heats of wetting of the fresh samples, the heats of adsorption of monolayers (from liquid phase) were calculated. Dividing these by the weights of water (or methyl alcohol) in the monolayers, the amounts of heat per gram of water (or methyl alcohol) adsorbed in the monolayer could be obtained. For example, in the case of silica gel (surface area = $339.7\text{ m}^2/\text{g}$.) the amounts of water and methyl alcohol required to form monolayers are 0.1017 g . and 0.1132 g . respectively. Bare silica gel evolves 25.75 and 38.25 cal./g . adsorbent when wetted by water and methyl alcohol respectively. From the curves plotted in Fig. 1 for the silica gel it is estimated that one gram of the gel, on which 0.1017 g . of water and 0.1132 g . of methyl alcohol are already adsorbed, would evolve 6.50 and 12.50 cal . on wetting with water and methyl alcohol respectively. Hence, to cause a monolayer of water and methyl alcohol to be adsorbed (from the liquid phase) on the silica gel, the evolution of 19.25 and 25.75 cal./g . of the adsorbent or 189.6 and 227.5 cal./g . of water and methyl alcohol respectively would result.

The results obtained in case of the various adsorbents are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Heat of wetting by water and methyl alcohol in the formation of monolayer.

Adsorbent.	Heat produced of liquid in the formation of monolayer by		Adsorbent.	Heat produced of liquid in the formation of monolayer by	
	Water.	MeOH.		Water.	MeOH.
Alumina gel	181.4 cal./g.	207.0 cal./g.	Bentonite	157.4 cal./g.	200.6 cal./g.
Silica gel	189.6	227.5	Sugar charcoal	167.3	215.6
Chromic oxide gel	173.6	219.7	Pine charcoal	190.0	231.2
Ferric oxide gel	179.2	213.4	Cocoonut charcoal	179.9	221.3

It is seen that when a monolayer of water or methyl alcohol is added, the heat evolved per gram of a given liquid is of the same order in all the samples examined. Further, while the average value in the case of water is a little more than twice the heat of fusion,^o in the case of methyl alcohol it is nearly seven times the heat of fusion. It is evident therefore that there is no definite relationship between the heat of adsorption of a liquid in the monolayer and its heat of fusion, as appears to have been suggested by Stowe (*loc. cit.*) and Puri *et al.* (*loc. cit.*).

Calculation of Isosteric Heats of Adsorption.—It has been shown by Young *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) that it is possible to calculate isosteric heats of adsorption by means of the following equation derived from the work of Hill (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1949, 17, 520).

$$U_0 - U = \int_0^{N_s} q_{st}.dN_s - \Delta H_v,$$

where $U_0 - U$ is the difference in the heat of immersion of the clean solid and a solid with N_s adsorbed molecules and ΔH_v is the molar heat of vaporisation of the liquid. The isosteric heat is thus obtained by a graphical differentiation of $U_0 - U$ versus N_s plot.

FIG. 2

Isosteric heats of adsorption as a function of the amount of the liquid adsorbed.

The isosteric heat values calculated in this manner are plotted as a function of the amount of water (or methyl alcohol) adsorbed in Fig. 2 in the case of silica gel and sugar charcoal. Similar curves were obtained in the case of the other adsorbents but are not included for reasons of space. It is seen that the heat effect is positive at all stages of adsorption in every case. This observation is of particular interest in the case of adsorption of water on charcoal on account of the fact that several workers have reported both positive and negative heats of adsorption of water on various types of carbon (Bartell and Suggitt, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, 58, 36; Pierce and Smith, *ibid.*, 1948, 52, 1111, 1115; Pierce *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 455; Anderson and Emmett, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, 56, 753). The discrepancies were probably due to different nature of the carbon surfaces examined by them. If a surface is easily wetted by water, *i.e.*, contact angle is zero, the heat effect will be positive. If, on the other hand, it is not easily wetted, *i.e.*, a contact angle is formed, the adhesion of water to the surface will be less than the cohesion of water. Therefore in order to cause water to adhere to the adsorbent rather than to itself energy must be provided. This leads to negative heat of adsorption.

The isosteric heats for the adsorption of monolayers of water and methyl alcohol are marked X on the respective graphs for the silica gel and sugar charcoal, plotted in Fig. 2. The values are evidently positive (*i.e.* the total heats of adsorption are greater

than the corresponding heats of liquefaction) but they tend to drop to zero (*i.e.*, the total heats of adsorption tend to approach the corresponding heats of liquefaction) as second and subsequent statistical surface layers are formed. These observations are in accordance with the requirements of the BET theory.

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